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ACKR3 expression during TE lineage commitment in human embryonic stem cells.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of ACKR3 as a lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.